

organic C, 0.04% total N) of the experimental field was loamy sand (Typic Ustochrept) with an average percolation rate of 4 mm/h.

N as urea was applied in 3 equal splits: at transplanting and 21 and 42 d

after transplanting. A basal dose of 13 kg P and 12 kg K/ha was applied at last puddling.

All the 3 varieties responded up to 150 kg N/ha. PR108 significantly outyielded PR106 at all N levels (see

table). Yield components also were highest in PR108. PR108 matures 6-8 d earlier than PR106, an advantage for early sowing of wheat in a rice - wheat cropping system. □

Performance of overage seedlings at different N levels

D. M. Maurya and M. P. Yadav, N. D. University of Agriculture and Technology, Crop Research Station, Masodha, Faizabad, U. P., India

We studied the effect of N level on grain yield and yield parameters using overage seedlings of four transplanted rice varieties - Mahsuri, Sarjoo 52, Ratna, and Saket 4 in a randomized block design with four replications.

Experimental plot soil was sandy loam with pH 7.5, EC (1:2) 0.09 mmho/cm, 0.42% organic C, 17.5 kg available P/ha, and 135 kg available K/ha. Fifty-five-day-old seedlings were transplanted 10 Aug 1983 at 2-3 seedlings/hill at 20 × 10-cm spacing. Urea was applied at 0, 50, and 100 kg N/ha. Single superphosphate and muriate of potash at 18 and 32 kg/ha were basally applied.

Each increment of N significantly increased panicle number, panicle

Yield and yield attributes of overage seedlings of 4 varieties as influenced by N level. Masodha, India.

Treatment	Panicles/m ²	Panicle weight (g)	1000-grain weight (g)	Plant height (cm)	Grain yield (t/ha)
N level (kg/ha)					
0	35	1.6	20.3	73	1.5
50	44	1.7	20.9	82	2.4
100	52	2.0	21.7	90	2.9
CD (0.05)	7.0	0.2	0.3	3	0.1
Variety					
Mahsuri	42	1.7	15.2	94	2.6
Sarjoo 52	35	2.3	27.1	77	2.3
Ratna	41	1.7	21.6	79	2.1
Saket 4	54	1.3	20.1	77	1.9
CD (0.05)	4	0.3	0.4	3	0.1

weight, test weight, plant height, and grain yield (see table), but average N use efficiency was low, 17.7 kg grain/kg N with 50 kg N/ha and 14.1 kg grain/kg N with 100 kg N/ha. In general, grain yield and yield parameters were adversely affected by planting overage seedlings, which resulted in low grain yields for all varieties. Long-duration Mahsuri performed better than medium

Sarjoo 52 and short Ratna and Saket 4. Although Sarjoo 52 yields higher than other varieties under normal conditions, Mahsuri performed better under these conditions, probably because its longer duration gave sufficient growth and development time to overcome late seedling planting. N application was beneficial to grain yield, even with overage seedlings. □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

GRAIN QUALITY

Two promising scented rice varieties for the Mekong Delta

Nguyen Xuan Hien and Nguyen Zhu Ha, Plant Breeding Department, Institute of Agricultural Technology of South Vietnam, Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam

Two promising scented rice varieties — Nang-thom sel. and Nang-huong-ran sel. — have been released for specific areas in the Mekong Delta. The varieties are suitable for the early Jul - late Dec crop in various waterlogged ricefields.

Nang-huong-ran sel. is distinguished

Table 1. Agricultural characteristics and grain quality of promising scented varieties. Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam.

Character	Nang-thom sel.	Nang-huong-ran sel.
Culm length (cm)	141.8	145.6
Growth duration (d)	160.3	165.3
Panicles/plant	10.6	7.3
Panicle length (cm)	23.7	23.6
Fully filled spikelets/panicle	108.0	131.3
1000-grain wt (g)	23.4	24.9
Grain yield (t/ha)	3.85	4.88
Culm strength ^b	5-7	1-3
Brown rice length (mm)	7.03	6.62
Brown rice length-to-width ratio	3.36	3.22
Chakiness ^b	1	1
Scent ^b	2	1

^aAv of 4-yr trials. ^bStandard evaluation system for rice codes.

by strong culms and large and dark green leaves. It grows well in light acid sulfate soils, but has a rather long growth duration. Nang-thom sel. meets all the requirements of Asian rice consumers (Table 1). Gross income for Nang-thom sel. is about 50% higher than that for Nang-huong-ran sel. and other common scented rices.

More than 40 samples of 22 scented varieties were collected from 11 provinces in the south and screened in a 4-yr project.

The two new varieties confirmed yield and grain quality superiorities over cultivars in testing in relatively large areas during two recent seasons (Table 2). □

Table 2. Yields of scented varieties in on-farm trials in Vietnam.

Cooperative	Yield (t/ha)		
	Nang-thom sel.	Nang-huong-ran sel.	Check ^a
Thanh Loc (Ho Chi Minh city)	3.6 (135)	3.9 (150)	2.6 (100)
An Lac (HCM city)	3.4 (118)	–	2.9 (100)
An Phu Tay (HCM city)	3.0 (125)	3.5 (137)	2.4 (100)
My Le (Long An Province)	3.3 (115)	3.8 (131)	2.9 (100)

^a Local scented varieties. Figures in parentheses are % of local check.

The International Rice Research Newsletter and the IRRI Reporter are mailed free to qualified individuals and institutions engaged in rice production and training. For further information write: IRRI, Communication and Publications Dept., Division R, P. O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines.

Molecular basis for puffing quality of rice

B. Thayumanavan, Biochemistry Department, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 641003, India

High-amylose varieties such as Bhavani and IR50 are preferred for making puffed rice. We compared the molecular properties of amylose and amylopectin in Bhavani and IR50 with those in CO 25, ASD7, and Ponni, which are preferred for making rice flakes, *idli*, and cooked rice.

The amylopectin of Bhavani showed a longer chain than the other varieties studied (Table 1). The chain length of amylose was not determined.

The amylose and amylopectin isolated from these varieties were treated with

Table 1. Amylose percentage and chain length of amylopectin in rice varieties.^a Coimbatore, India.

Variety	Amylose (%)	Chain length (no. of glucose/branch)
Bhavani	30.0	26
IR50	27.6	23
CO 25	27.3	22
Ponni	27.2	22
ASD7	29.5	21
LSD	0.48	0.95

^a Each value represents the average of triplicate analysis.

Table 2. Percentage hydrolysis of amylose and amylopectin by salivary α -amylase at different time intervals.^a Coimbatore, India.

Variety	Component	Percentage hydrolysis at indicated time				
		30 min	60 min	120 min	240 min	360 min
Bhavani	A	51.8	62.1	66.2	86.0	93.2
	AP	50.0	59.6	59.6	61.9	65.3
IR50	A	49.7	65.3	79.0	84.9	88.0
	AP	48.2	50.4	51.8	56.2	65.3
Ponni	A	41.4	53.6	65.0	79.7	83.9
	AP	48.2	48.9	49.4	55.7	62.1
ASD7	A	43.5	51.8	60.1	66.2	66.2
	AP	38.3	43.5	49.4	56.9	57.9
CO 25	A	21.8	34.7	43.3	50.8	54.9
	AP	38.3	44.2	52.2	59.0	66.2
LSD	A	0.7 (between varieties)				
	AP	0.8 (between varieties)				

^a Each value represents the average of duplicate analysis. A = amylose, AP = amylopectin.

alpha-amylase and the amount of reducing sugars released was measured across time. The rate of release of reducing sugars from the amylose of Bhavani and IR50 was faster than in the

other varieties (Table 2). For amylopectin, the rate of release of reducing sugars was faster for Bhavani. □

High-yielding aromatic rice variety GR101

N. D. Desai, S. Raman, M. U. Kukadia, and M. R. Patel, National Agricultural Research Project, Gujarat Agricultural University, Navsari 396453, Gujarat, India

GR 101, selected from segregating

material of IR8/Pankhali 203 cross, was released in 1986. The new variety has maintained its superior performance at all locations (Table 1). It has yielded 4.1 t/ha, 83.6% more than Pankhali 203.

GR101 has long, slender, fine grains with an oily translucent kernel and mild aroma (Table 2). It has resistance to neck blast. □